

Quantitation of Uranyl Ion by Paper Chromatographic Technique

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A paper chromatographic technique has been adopted to separate $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ from $\text{Th}(\text{IV})$, $\text{Ce}(\text{III})$, $\text{Fe}(\text{III})$ and $\text{Zr}(\text{IV})$ in binary and ternary combinations using a solvent consisting of chloroform acetone-amyl alcohol and concentrated hydrochloric acid (12:6:6:1v/v). A direct photodensitometric method of evaluating unknown quantitatively from strips run simultaneously for known and unknown has been described, which proved better in comparison to other known methods of direct spot evaluation. The procedure appears to be useful for estimating $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ within concentration range $< 50 \mu\text{g}$.

PAPER chromatographic separation of metal ions can not be utilised for quantitation work unless it fulfills certain conditions of well demarked zone or spot formations. Most of the earlier work reported in this direction is concerned with indirect methods of estimating separated spots or zones by techniques such as colorimetry, polarography, titrimetry, spectrophotometry etc. after their elution from the paper strips¹⁻³.

Such methods not only involve the errors during elution process, but also include the expected limits of errors of these estimation techniques. It is worthwhile, therefore, to estimate the separated spots on the filter paper by direct scanning with an instrument like photodensitometer.

The few references for uranium estimation after its paper chromatographic separation, include estimations of uranium by visual comparison method⁴, polarography⁵, complexometric titrations⁶ using E.D.T.A. and colorimetry⁷ after elution of the separated spot. A method of direct assessment suitable for determining this metal ion by photodensitometry has not been used so far. This paper reports the findings about the use of a chloroformic solvent for quantitation of uranyl ion by paper chromatography in presence of ions such as thorium, cerium, zirconium and iron using a procedure of direct scanning for the developed spots.

Experimental

The solvent system chosen after several preliminary experiments consisted of a combination of chloroform-acetone-amyl alcohol and hydrochloric acid (conc.) in the ratio 12 : 6 : 6 : 1 on v/v basis. This solvent was used to determine the R_f values of all the ions investigated and also for further separation work. Ascending paper chromatography has been used for all experiments throughout this work. Sheets of Whatman No. 1 (23 × 9 cm) were used in this procedure. Glass jars provided with well greased glass lids for making the chamber airtight and fitted with

movable all glass hangers were used for development.

A pencil line was drawn across the paper-strip at a distance of 3 cms away from the starting edge. Five equidistant pencil points were marked on this line for spotting the known and unknown samples. Solutions of uranyl ion (as its nitrate) of different concentrations (10-50 μg for each drop volume) were spotted by a micropipette (drop volume 0.001 ml) on the line at the points 1, 2, 4 and 5. The solution of unknown concentration was spotted at point 3. The paper was quickly dried by using a cold air blower.

A time interval of 3½ hr was allowed for development. The chromatogram was then taken out from the jar, dried quickly and exposed to ammonia vapours for neutralising the acid content of the paper. It was then sprayed with 2.0% w/v aqueous solution of potassium ferrocyanide, which formed rich brown coloured derivative with the developed spots of uranyl ion. After drying, the paper-strip was cut horizontally and a narrow strip of 2 × 9 cm size containing all the five developed spots was fed to the photodensitometer (manufactured by Systronix Ltd., India, Type 201). Each spot was scanned carefully and repeatedly. The optical densities were recorded. Curves of optical densities against distance of strip moved in densitometer were plotted for each spot. The peak-heights were measured which were then plotted against the metal ion concentration to give a calibration curve. Unknown was calculated with the help of this calibration plot. As the unknown and the standards were run simultaneously here, the value of optical density for the known and the unknown were obtained under similar conditions of experimentation.

Using the above technique of development and scanning of chromatographed spots, mixtures of $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ with $\text{Th}(\text{IV})$, $\text{Ce}(\text{III})$, $\text{Fe}(\text{III})$, and $\text{Zr}(\text{IV})$ were used in binary (1 : 1 on conc. basis) as well as ternary (1 : 1 : 1 on conc. basis) combinations for

Fig. 1

putting the spots for the unknown. The solvent used here gave clear cut separation of ions (refer to R_f values) with compact spots and desired shapes necessary for quantitative work. The R_f data ($R_f \times 100$) of the ions under study for this solvent system is given below :

$UO_2(II) = 16.5$, $Th(IV) = 4.2$, $Ce(III) = 2.5$,
 $Fe(III) = 52.0$, and $Zr(IV) = 0.00$.

Results and Discussion

The results of such estimations have been shown in figure 1(a) for calibration and evaluation for the estimation of $UO_2(II)$ in combination with $Th(IV)$, and 1(b) for peak height determination. Similar graphs (not given for the sake of brevity) were obtained for $UO_2(II)$ estimation in presence of $Ce(III)$, $Fe(III)$ and $Zr(IV)$ ions also. The results of the unknown concentrations of $UO_2(II)$ present was read off from the straight line calibration plots similar to 1(b). The error analysis has been done and is reported in Table I. Similar (graphs not included) estimations were done for ternary combination also (see Table I).

As the method is applicable with much accuracy at the concentration limits between 10 to 50 µg, the method can be regarded quite satisfactory for $UO_2(II)$ determination on drop scale. As compared to other estimation procedures⁹⁻¹⁵ the technique used here is quick and involves comparatively less error $\pm 3\%$. The solvent used was particularly good in giving round and compact spots with no tailing whatsoever.

There are several other methods also to evaluate a spot on a paper chromatogram⁸⁻¹⁵. Hence, to

show the comparative usefulness of the method described above, the evaluation of the obtained spots was done by these methods also. Table 2

TABLE I

Ion combination	Value for $UO_2(II)$ ion in µg		Error %
	Theoretical	Experimental	
$UO_2(II)-Th(IV)$	30.0	29.5	-1.66
$UO_2(II)-Ce(III)$	30.0	31.0	+3.33
$UO_2(II)-Fe(III)$	30.0	31.0	+3.33
$UO_2(II)-Zr(IV)$	30.0	31.0	+3.33
$UO_2(II)-Fe(III) \& Th(IV)$	30.0	30.5	+1.66
$UO_2(II)-Fe(III) \& Ce(III)$	30.0	31.0	+3.33
$UO_2(II)-Fe(III) \& Zr(IV)$	30.0	31.0	+3.33

gives a comparison of results by different methods. Methods based on spot area measurements (i.e., A & F) and modified procedures of Fowler and

TABLE 2

Methods	Error%
A. Spot area measurement method ⁸	± 14.4
B. Fowler's method ⁹	± 22.0
C. Miyaki's method ¹⁰	± 4.0
D. Total colour density method ¹¹	± 1.8
E. Maximum colour density method ¹²	± 1.66
F. Spot area $\times$ maximum colour density method ^{11, 13, 14, 15} .	± 4.16

Miyaki (i.e., B & C) in general involve greater percentage of error, making it obviously evident that method used here is better than others. It is far more accurate for estimating uranyl ion by paper chromatographic procedures. Method D, which depends on the principle of measuring total colour density is obviously good as in this one scans the complete area covered by the optical density graphs. The method E is same as used in this work and hence usefulness and superiority of the technique is evident.

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